

Supporting Information:

Structural and optoelectronic properties of Sb₂S₂O
based photodetectors

Borna Radatović^{1‡}, Fedor Lipilin^{1‡}, Amutha Subramani¹, Aljoscha Söll¹, Kseniia Mosina¹, Kalaiarasan Meganathan¹, Lukas Kolacny², Martin Vesely², Jan Luxa¹, Zdeněk Sofer^{1*}*

¹ Department of Inorganic Chemistry, University of Chemistry and Technology Prague,
Technicka 5, 166 28 Prague 6, Czech Republic

² Department of Organic Technology, University of Chemistry and Technology Prague,
Technicka 5, 166 28 Prague 6, Czech Republic

Figure 11. Schematic of device fabrication. (a) Nitto tape is placed on top of the Sb_2S_2O bulk crystal. (b) After detaching Nitto tape from surface, PDMS is pressed on surface with exfoliated Sb_2S_2O . (c) Sb_2S_2O flakes are located on PDMS after detaching from Nitto tape. (d) PDMS/ Sb_2S_2O is positioned with an XYZ manipulator over the targeted area on the patterned substrate and connected and pressed slightly to ensure uniform adhesion to the substrate. (e) PDMS is slowly separated with a z-axis manipulator leaving Sb_2S_2O on a new substrate. (f) Sb_2S_2O is transferred onto the patterned substrate.

Figure S2. TEM images of exfoliated $\text{Sb}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}$. 100,000x, 250,000x and 800,000x magnification on (a), (b) and (c) respectively.

Figure S3. DFT calculations of Raman spectrum. (a) Optimised structure of the $\text{Sb}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}$, the bulk triclinic phase with lattice parameter $a = 6.061 \text{ \AA}$ $b = 8.238 \text{ \AA}$ and $c = 11.074 \text{ \AA}$ with the space group of P1. (b) Calculated Raman spectrum with most intense peaks at 33.98 cm^{-1} and 308.57 cm^{-1} , indicated by black and red arrows, respectively.

Figure S4. EDS map of $\text{Sb}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}$ device. (a) SEM image of the area used for EDS mapping. (b) Sb ($\text{L}\alpha 1$) elemental map. (c) S ($\text{K}\alpha 1$) elemental map. (d) Au ($\text{M}\alpha 1$) elemental map. (e) Si ($\text{K}\alpha 1$) elemental map. (f) O ($\text{K}\alpha 1$) elemental map.

Figure S5. Optical images of $\text{Sb}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}$ devices with graphene contacts. (a) Non-encapsulated device with graphene electrodes. (b) Encapsulated device with graphene electrodes, with indicated encapsulating hBN with red dashed line.

Figure S6. Photoresponse for 470 nm wavelength illumination with $P=1\text{mW}$. Experimental data was used to determine photoresponse under turning illumination on/off. The illumination period of 30 seconds is indicated by a yellow area, on which start and end, photoresponse exponential rise and decay are indicated with green and red, respectively. The determined device rise time is around $t_r \approx 400\text{ ms}$ and fall time $t_f \approx 600\text{ ms}$.

Figure S7. The simulated electric field across the $\text{Sb}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}$ device for incident light of 375 nm, 385 nm, 405 nm and 415 nm wavelength on (a), (b), (c) and (d), respectively.